

A STUDY ON THE POST COVID EFFECT ON FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY IN KERALA

A Report

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award

of

POST DOCTORAL FELLOW

By

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MAY 2022

Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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Certificate

This is to certify that entitled **A Study on The Post Covid Effect on Food Processing Industry in Kerala** submitted by **Dr. Deeja S** to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the Post Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by him under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

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Acknowledgements

I wish to express my profound sense of gratitude to my supervising teacher, **Dr. P S Aithal**, Department of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Srinivas Nagar, Mangalore without whose skillful guidance expert advice, this report would not have appeared in the present form. I am deeply indebted to him for the earnest interest he had shown in me and in my academic effort.

I acknowledge my sincere thanks to **Dr. Praveen B M**, Research Director, Srinivas University, Srinivas Nagar, Mangalore for holding me to a high research standard and enforcing for good research result.

I am indebted to **Rev. Fr. Baby Thomas**, Manager, St. Gregorios College, Kottarakara for giving me the consent to do Post-Doctoral research.

I also extended my thanks to **Mrs. Jiji Peter**, Principal, **Dr. Sumi Alex**, Assistant Professor & H.O.D. and **Dr Soumya Syamchand** for providing the facility of undertaking my work smoothly. I also thank my colleagues at the Department of Commerce.

I have visited a number of institutions and libraries as part of research and received warm welcome and co-operation from all of them. Though it is difficult to name all these persons in this short acknowledgement, I simply wish to state their wholehearted co-operation has benefited my research in numerous ways.

I gratefully remember my parents, sister, my husband **Gurudeva Sajan** and daughters **K.Sanvi** and **K. Saivi**, who were a source of inspiration throughout this endeavour.

I know well that in this brief acknowledgement, I could not include all persons who provide me with data and congenial atmosphere to work with concentration. I express my heartfelt thanks to all those whom I could not mention in these pages.

CONTENTS

	Page
Acknowledgements	
List of Tables	v-vi
Synopsis	viii-xii
Chapters	
1. Introduction	1-6
2. Review of Earlier Studies	7-9
3. Cost Structure Analysis and Profitability	10-35
4. Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Suggestions	36-40
Bibliography	41-42
Publications from the Report	43-57

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title of the Table	Page
1	Distribution of cost of raw materials(fruits) based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	
2	Distribution of cost of raw materials(fruits) based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
3	Distribution of cost of raw materials(vegetables) based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	
4	Distribution of cost of raw materials(vegetables) based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
5	Distribution of total cost of raw materials(fruit sand vegetables) based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	
6	Distribution of total cost of raw materials(fruit sand vegetables) based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
7	Distribution of salary of permanent workers based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	
8	Distribution of salary of permanent workers based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
9	Distribution of salary of temporary workers based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	
10	Distribution of salary of temporary workers based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
11	Distribution of salary of technical workers based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	

12	Distribution of salary of technical workers based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
13	Distribution of total labour cost based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	
14	Distribution of total labour cost based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
15	Distribution of total cost of service based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	
16	Distribution of total cost of service based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
17	Distribution of total cost of packing based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19	
18	Distribution of total cost of packing based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19	
19	Distribution ranking of raw material problems	
20	Distribution ranking of labour problems	
21	Distribution of gross profit ratio based on selected variables	
22	Distribution of net profit ratio based on selected variables	
23	Distribution of return on investment based on selected variables	
24	Distribution of profit volume ratio based on selected variables	

SYNOPSIS OF THE PROPOSED RESEARCH WORK
A STUDY ON THE POST COVID EFFECT ON FOOD PROCESSING
INDUSTRY IN KERALA

INTRODUCTION

Food processing is the set of methods and techniques used to transform raw ingredients into food or to transform food into other forms for consumptions by humans or animals either in the home or by the food processing industry. Food processing dates back to the prehistoric ages when crude processing incorporates slaughtering, fermenting, sun drying, preserving with salt and various types of cooking. In the 20th century, World War II, the space race and rising consumer society in the country contributed to the growth of food processing industry. The second half of the 20th century witnessed a rise in the pursuit of convenience food processor especially marketed their product to middle class working wives and mothers.

The Ministry of Food Processing Industry was set up in the year 1988 with a view to develop a strong and vibrant food processing industry and to create increased employment in the rural sector and enables the farmers to reap the benefit of modern technology, creation of surplus for exports and stimulating demand for processed food.

The ongoing global pandemic has left no sector untouched by its wave of impacts. While the number of people being affected by Covid-19 still continues to climb, it is needless to comprehend the pandemics grave impacts on every corner of the nation's economy. With almost all the segments having fallen prey to the uncertain impacts of Covid-19, even the food and beverage industry in India is responding to the ongoing crisis by bracing itself for Corona virus impacts.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Goldar (1988) in one of the books entitled "Relative efficiency of modern small scale industries in India" revealed that small scale units are efficient only in those industries in which difference in the capital – labour ratio between large scale and small scale units are relatively low. The study found that small scale, create more employment than large scale,

but small scale units are less efficient in the use of capital in almost all industries. Small scale units are relatively inefficient compared to large scale units. Relative efficiency index is found to be positively related to size.

Gurumoorthy and Jayachandran (2002) studied the progress of small scale industry in terms of production employment and exports. And compared sick units in SSI sector with sick units in non SSI sector and review the reason for the sickness in SSI sector. It analyzed the financial assistance provided by commercial bank to SSI sector. The main reasons of sickness are lack of working capital, lack of technical know how and inefficient management system. Financial supports by the bank are not sufficient to meet the working of SSI units. Hence government should take active participation is granting extra help to the SSI units.

Ram.P. Aneja Balachandran (2007) in an article entitled “Fruit and vegetable sector – production, processing and marketing potential and prospective”, mentioned that the main hurdle of fruit and vegetable product is the low purchasing power of the Indian consumer. By encouraging and providing support to the farmers who were the real owners of these industry, the full potential of the industry can be achieved. More quality raw materials can be produced by giving support. Crunch on employment in this sector are slow growth and rapid decline in the share of agriculture. Marketing and lacking of preservation facilities are the main bottlenecks of this industry.

Rajat (2008) in the book entitled “Changing face of processed food industry in India” outlined present status of processed food industry of India by showing that low level of technology, lack of automation and low productivity make the processed food more costlier. In the United States 90 per cent of food processing units are owned and run as family business, but it is not possible for the third generation business in India due to lack of core competencies and strategic alliance. The author pointed out that the product that goes through transformation and brand got support and patronage of consumer then they become the international power brand. Brand name got customer support and patronage only if the products got always transformation. Many of the domestic companies have disappeared from the scene because of the high taxation, non availability of infrastructure, lack of quality raw material, lack of latest packaging material etc. This results in the monopoly of multinational companies in Indian market. Intense competitive activity of multinationals in

food processing industry resulted in the increase of market size and improvement in the quality and variety of products.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Kerala is blessed with bounty of agricultural produces like spices, coconut, rubber, coffee, tea, cardamom, pepper, areca nut and other hill products, Considering the emerging market for organic food, both domestic and international, the State has an enormous capacity to cater the market with quality products. Food Processing Industry is regarded as the ‘Sunrise Industry’ of the State and Kerala has a fairly strong base of food processing industries. This sector plays a major role in the economic development of the State and various studies reveal that its contribution to output and value added and employment increased during the recent years. The turnover of Food Processing Sector accounts for Rs 3,50,000 crores approximately and within the value added food products estimated at Rs 90,000 crores. Government of Kerala took interest in the Food processing Industry, as a result of this Kinfra food processing industrial park was established at Kochi and Kozhikode and several subsidy scheme was introduced to start industries in Kerala. The units employ more than 40,000 people and have a total turnover of Rs.6,000 crores. Some of the units are also involved in exports and earn more than Rs.700 crores from export business. Higher income levels, a large young population and changes in the life patterns imply that demand for processed is high. Ministry of Food Processing industry classified food processing industry mainly into the following categories. Fish and fish products, meat and poultry, fruits and vegetables, milk and milk products, grains, alcoholic beverages, plantations, other consumer product groups like confectionary, chocolates and cocoa products, soya product etc. Kerala has the supply of wide variety of fruits and vegetables. Seasonal availability of fruits and vegetables naturally lead to wastage. Wastage occurs also on account of the lack of demand for the primary products in their original form. Value addition and processing can have the effect of inducing demand for these food processing industry adds value to the primary products.

The diverse culture, traditions and religions in Kerala has given birth to a wide variety of ethnic foods across the state. Alike spices, ethnic foods of Kerala also has gained worldwide acceptance. As the non-resident population of Kerala is huge, export opportunities for ethnic food is also tremendous in nature. This will ultimately result in creating larger employment opportunities for the ethnic sections of population. As this is a major source of

income for the ethnic communities in Kerala, this can have an impact on the economic front. Thus focusing more on this area and giving importance in developing policies related to ethnic food export is an important measure which has to be given emphasis

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Fruits and vegetables play an important role in human diet and nutrition. They are indispensable source of essential dietary nutrients, vitamins and nutrients. According to the official status India exported processed fruits and vegetables worth 6240 million in 2018-19. According to the ministry of food industry, there are about 6200 food processing industry in India. Among them, 17 per cent of these units are large scale and remaining operates from home cottage and small industry. The Kerala state is exporting around 30000 MT. Vegetables and fruits which offer excellent opportunity for the production of quality products in the state. During the pandemic, people world over have realised, the importance of immunity booster food products. India is one of the largest producers of herbal, medicinal, organic food. The agriculture export policy launched in 2018 also focuses on cluster based export promotion of novel, indigenous, organic, ethnic, traditional and non-traditional agro products including value added perishables

Fruit and vegetable processing is a sunrise sector in the state. But this industry is caught in the vicious cycle of inefficiency due to low productivity, under capacity utilisation and rising cost of production and also apathy of food processors to quality and safety issues and ineffective regulatory mechanism. The absence of well organised setup for marketing the product is another serious problem faced by the industry.

It is in this context, that the need of a study to highlight the areas of fruits and vegetable units that require immediate and proper attention of the policy makers and with those who are entrusted with the task and welfare of FPI in Kerala. So far no systematic study has been done, so the present study is proposed.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the cost structure of FPIs.
2. To study the profitability analysis of FPIs
3. To study the production problems of FPIs

METHODOLOGY

Fruits and vegetable processing industries spread over 14 revenue district of the Kerala constitute the population of the study. For the purpose of the study the state is divided into 3 regions namely Southern, Central and Northern regions. The study area is mainly concentrated on large scale sector of the FPIs units. Southern region consisting of Thrivananthapuram, Kollam, Pathanamthitta, Alappuzha and Kottayam Districts from them Alappuzha is selected having of 2 large scale units. Central region consisting of Ernakulam, Thrissur, Idukki and Palakkad, Ernakulam consist of 8 large scale units and northern region consisting of Kozhikode, Wayanad, Kasargodu, Malappuram and Kannur, Kozhikode district having 3 units. Census method will be study for the study purpose.

The study will make use of both primary and secondary data. Primary data will be collected with be collected with the help of properly designed interview schedule. Secondary data will be collected from magazines, journals, publications of Government and Ministry of Food Processing Industry etc.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Food processing is the set of methods and techniques used to transform raw ingredients into food or to transform food into other forms for consumptions by humans or animals either in the home or by the food processing industry. Food processing dates back to the prehistoric ages when crude processing incorporates slaughtering, fermenting, sun drying, preserving with salt and various types of cooking. In the 20th century, World War II, the space race and rising consumer society in the country contributed to the growth of food processing industry. The second half of the 20th century witnessed a rise in the pursuit of convenience food processor especially marketed their product to middle class working wives and mothers.

Food processing industry in India is a sunrise sector. Availability of raw materials, changing life styles and relaxation in policies has given a considerable push to the industry's growth. Food processing industry help in improve the value of agricultural products, ensures remunerative prices to farmers and at the same time create favourable demand for Indian agricultural products in the world market. Indian food processing industry has been significant growth and changes over the past few years, driven by changing trends in markets, consumer segments and regulations. These trends such as changing demographics, growing population and rapid urbanization are expected to continue in the future and therefore it will shape the demand for value added products and thus for food processing industry in India. Food processing industry accounts for about 14% of manufacturing GDP i.e., Rs 280000 crores and employs about 13 million people directly and 35 million people indirectly. Very good investment opportunities exist in many areas of food processing industry. Important among them are fruit and vegetable processing industry, meat, fish and poultry processing, milk products, convenience food and drinks etc. food processing industry has many challenges in front of it, ranging from infrastructure to human resources and technological backwardness. India will miss a golden opportunity of using its vast agri livestock resources to strengthen its economy.

The Ministry of Food Processing Industry was set up in the year 1988 with a view to develop a strong and vibrant food processing industry and to create increased employment in the rural sector and enables the farmers to reap the benefit of modern technology, creation of surplus for exports and stimulating demand for processed food.

1.1 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Kerala is blessed with bounty of agricultural produces like spices, coconut, rubber, coffee, tea, cardamom, pepper, areca nut and other hill products, Considering the emerging market for organic food, both domestic and international, the State has an enormous capacity to cater the market with quality products. Food Processing Industry is regarded as the ‘Sunrise Industry’ of the State and Kerala has a fairly strong base of food processing industries. This sector plays a major role in the economic development of the State and various studies reveal that its contribution to output and value added and employment increased during the recent years. The turnover of Food Processing Sector accounts for Rs 3,50,000 crores approximately and within the value-added food products estimated at Rs 90,000 crores. Government of Kerala took interest in the Food processing Industry, as a result of this Kinfra food processing industrial park was established at Kochi and Kozhikode and several subsidy schemes was introduced to start industries in Kerala. The units employ more than 40,000 people and have a total turnover of Rs.6,000 crores. Some of the units are also involved in exports and earn more than Rs.700 crores from export business. Higher income levels, a large young population and changes in the life patterns imply that demand for processed is high. Ministry of Food Processing industry classified food processing industry mainly into the following categories. Fish and fish products, meat and poultry, fruits and vegetables, milk and milk products, grains, alcoholic beverages, plantations, other consumer product groups like confectionary, chocolates and cocoa products, soya product etc. Kerala has the supply of wide variety of fruits and vegetables. Seasonal availability of fruits and vegetables naturally lead to wastage. Wastage occurs also on account of the lack of demand for the primary products in their original form. Value addition and processing can have the effect of inducing demand for these food processing industries adds value to the primary products.

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front. Thus focusing more on this area and giving importance in developing policies related to ethnic food export is an important measure which has to be given emphasis

1.2 RESEARCH PROBLEM

Fruits and vegetables play an important role in human diet and nutrition. They are indispensable source of essential dietary nutrients, vitamins and nutrients. According to the official status India exported processed fruits and vegetables worth 6240 million in 2018-19. According to the ministry of food industry, there are about 6200 food processing industry in India. Among them, 17 per cent of these units are large scale and remaining operates from home cottage and small industry. The Kerala state is exporting around 30000 MT. Vegetables and fruits which offer excellent opportunity for the production of quality products in the state. During the pandemic, people world over have realised, the importance of immunity booster food products. India is one of the largest producers of herbal, medicinal, organic food. The agriculture export policy launched in 2018 also focuses on cluster based export promotion of novel, indigenous, organic, ethnic, traditional and non-traditional agro products including value added perishables

Fruit and vegetable processing is a sunrise sector in the state. But this industry is caught in the vicious cycle of inefficiency due to low productivity, under capacity utilisation and rising cost of production and also apathy of food processors to quality and safety issues and ineffective regulatory mechanism. The absence of well organised setup for marketing the product is another serious problem faced by the industry.

It is in this context, that the need of a study to highlight the areas of fruits and vegetable units that require immediate and proper attention of the policy makers and with those who are entrusted with the task and welfare of FPI in Kerala. So far no systematic study has been done, so the present study is proposed.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is an attempt to understand the working of fruit and vegetable processing industry in Kerala. Fruit and vegetable industry is one of the major components of food processing industry. The technological aspects of the fruit and vegetable industry are beyond the purview of the study. The study focuses on the functional areas of the industry. It mainly

concentrates to study the impact of Covid -19 on the cost structure and profitability of the fruit and vegetable processing in Kerala.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of the study are mention below.

- 1.To study the cost structure of fruit and vegetable processing units in Kerala.
2. To study the profitability of fruit and vegetable processing units in Kerala.
3. To study the production problem of fruit and vegetable processing units in Kerala.

1.5 METHODOLOGY

Fruits and vegetable processing industries spread over 14 revenue district of the Kerala constitute the population of the study. For the purpose of the study the state is divided into 3 regions namely Southern, Central and Northern regions. The study area is mainly concentrated on large scale sector of the FPIs units. Southern region consisting of Thiruvananthapuram, Kollam, Pathanamthitta, Alappuzha and Kottayam Districts from them Alappuzha is selected having of 2 large scale units. Central region consisting of Ernakulam, Thrissur, Idukki and Palakkad, Ernakulam consist of 8 large scale units and northern region consisting of Kozhikode, Wayanad, Kasargodu, Malappuram and Kannur, Kozhikode district having 3 units. Census method is used for the study.

The study will make use of both primary and secondary data. Primary data will be collected with be collected with the help of properly designed interview schedule. Secondary data will be collected from magazines, journals, publications of Government and Ministry of Food Processing Industry etc.

1.6 TOOLS OF ANALYSIS

Primary data collected were edited, coded, tabulated and analyzed with the help of a computer using SPSS/DC keeping in view of the objectives of study. Certain mathematical and statistical tools were used for the study include percentage, mean, standard deviation and F test.

1.7 VARIABLES USED FOR THE STUDY

1. Classification variables

- a) Region of units situated
- b) Number of products produced by the units
- c) Products wise classification of units.

2. Study variables

- a) Raw material cost
- b) Labour cost
- c) Cost of packing
- d) Cost of service
- e) Profitability

1.8 LIMITATION OF STUDY

The study has the following limitations

1. Most of industrial units did not maintain accurate records, gathering primary data was challenging. Primary data is mainly collected through an interview schedule and discussion with the entrepreneurs.
2. Some entrepreneurs were hesitant to offer necessary information about the functioning of the units.
3. Fruit and Vegetable processing industry is distributed throughout 14 districts, but the four major industries are concentrated in three districts, and the study was limited to these three districts exclusively.

The researcher, on the other hand, has gone to great lengths to guarantee that the study is free of bias and conducted in a systematic manner.

1.9 PRESENTATION OF THE STUDY

1. Chapter 1 narrates the significance, research problem, scope, objectives, research methodology, various tools and limitation of the study.
2. Chapter 2 deals with the review of earlier studies.
3. Chapter 3 deals with cost structure and profitability analysis.
4. Chapter 4 narrates the findings conclusion and suggestions.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF EARLIER STUDIES

Goldar (1988)¹ in one of the books entitled “Relative efficiency of modern small-scale industries in India” revealed that small scale units are efficient only in those industries in which difference in the capital – labour ratio between large scale and small scale units are relatively low. The study found that small scale, create more employment than large scale, but small scale units are less efficient in the use of capital in almost all industries. Small scale units are relatively inefficient compared to large scale units. Relative efficiency index is found to be positively related to size.

Gurumoorthy and Jayachandran (2002)² studied the progress of small scale industry in terms of production employment and exports. And compared sick units in SSI sector with sick units in non SSI sector and review the reason for the sickness in SSI sector. It analyzed the financial assistance provided by commercial bank to SSI sector. The main reasons of sickness are lack of working capital, lack of technical know how and inefficient management system. Financial supports by the bank are not sufficient to meet the working of SSI units. Hence government should take active participation is granting extra help to the SSI units.

Thomas Ohlsson (2002)³ in his book entitled “Minimal processing technologies in the food industry ” stated that, techniques used for minimally processed food are inefficient for the commercial stability for extended periods. The main requirement for the controlling of food decay is refrigeration and controlling of shelf – life. It is the responsibility of the manufacturer to ensure the shelf-life of the product and to determine whether the product is throughout the assigned shelf – life. Packaging used for minimally processed fruits and vegetables is a key operation. Now a days the mostly used packaging is MAP (Modified Atmosphere Packaging).

Ram.P. Aneja Balachandran (2007)⁴ in an article entitled “Fruit and vegetable sector – production, processing and marketing potential and prospective”, mentioned that the main hurdle of fruit and vegetable product is the low purchasing power of the Indian consumer. By encouraging and providing support to the farmers who were the real owners of these industry, the full potential of the industry can be achieved. More quality raw materials can

be produced by giving support. Crunch on employment in this sector are slow growth and rapid decline in the share of agriculture. Marketing and lacking of preservation facilities are the main bottlenecks of this industry.

Sudheer and Indira (2007)⁵ studied the magnitude of post-harvest loss of fruits and vegetables in their book “Post-harvest technology of horticulture crops”. In a developed country the range of post-harvest loss is only 5 to 25 per cent, but in a country like India, it ranges from 20 to 50 per cent, because of poor post-harvest practices. Post-harvest loss of fruit and vegetables can be classified into two primary and secondary. Primary loss includes; mechanical loss, pathological action, environmental functions etc. while secondary loss include inadequate harvesting, transportation, storage and marketing facilities. Magnitude of post-harvest loss can be reduced to some extent by implementing proper harvesting practices, adopting modern packing techniques, improved transportation, and latest marketing practices.

Rajat (2008)⁶ in the book entitled “Changing face of processed food industry in India” outlined present status of processed food industry of India by showing that low level of technology, lack of automation and low productivity make the processed food costlier. In the United States 90 per cent of food processing units are owned and run as family business, but it is not possible for the third generation business in India due to lack of core competencies and strategic alliance. The author pointed out that the product that goes through transformation and brand got support and patronage of consumer then they become the international power brand. Brand name got customer support and patronage only if the products got always transformation. Many of the domestic companies have disappeared from the scene because of the high taxation, non-availability of infrastructure, lack of quality raw material, lack of latest packaging material etc. This results in the monopoly of multinational companies in Indian market. Intense competitive activity of multinationals in food processing industry resulted in the increase of market size and improvement in the quality and variety of products.

Muhammad Siddiq (2012)⁷ stated that post-harvest handling of fresh fruits start with the harvesting, processing, transportation, reaching at the destination. In all these processes maintaining the quality of products is very much important. About 2% to 23% of post-harvest loss has occurred in developed countries between production and consumption sites. But in developing countries it reaches upto 50 per cent. Some of the current trends followed

in the industry are globalization of product marketing, increased demand for year-round supply of items with better flavor, increased demand for organic produce and locally produced goods, increased efforts to assure safety of food products etc.

CHAPTER III

COST STRUCTURE ANALYSIS AND PROFITABILITY

A COST STRUCTURE

The present chapter examines the cost structure profitability of fruit and vegetable processing units. The analysis is carried out with respect to the components of costs namely, raw materials, labour cost, cost of packing, and cost of service.

In general, cost means the amount of resource used in exchange for goods or service. The terminology of Chartered Institute of Management Accountants, London defines cost as the “amount of expenditure (actual or notional) Incurred on, or attributable to, a specified thing or activity”. The Institute of Management Accountant, USA says “cost is a measurement in monetary terms of the amount of resources used for some purposes”

Cost structure is simply the identification of cost associated with the production of goods or services are distributed throughout the process. Cost structure can be defined as “the relative proportion of its fixed and variable cost”

Costs are classified into two i.e., fixed and variable cost. Fixed cost is a cost which does not vary directly with output. It is also known as indirect or overhead cost. Variable cost is a cost which varies directly with the output. It is also known as direct cost or marginal cost. Variable costs include direct material, labour, and other direct expenses.

3.1 RAW MATERIALS COST ANALYSIS

Raw material is the basic material from which the product is manufactured or made. In fruit and vegetable processing units, raw materials utilized are highly perishable and seasonal in nature. Hence it should be processed as soon as it reaches the units. Mainly the raw materials contain fruits and vegetables. Data relating to the value of raw materials (fruits) purchased by the sample units are given below.

Table 1
Distribution of cost of raw materials (fruits) based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	852000.0	1655631.9	02	0.79	0.458
	Ernakulam	12386081.6	38687148.9	08		
	Kozhikode	8516655.2	24575940.4	03		
No of products produced	< 3	2566315.8	3184171.4	05	6.96**	0.002
	>=3	31804368.4	55108197.5	08		
Category	Vegetable	142772.7	514291.2	02	3.85*	0.025
	Fruit	15944842.1	48323417.0	02		
	Both	18581566.7	29346916.5	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

* Significant at 0.05 level

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in Table 1 shows that the average amount used for fruit purchased is high in Ernakulam district (12386081.6) and low in Alappuzha district (852000.0). The amount used for fruit purchasing is high in units where three or more than three products are produced (31804368.4) and low in units that produce less than three product (2566315.8). As the number of products producing increase the raw material used for producing the products also increases. The F test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=6.96).Units that producing both fruits & Vegetables products, have high average amount (18581566.7) and low in units that produce only vegetable products (142772.7). F test exhibit significant variation at 0.05 level (F=3.85).

Table 2
Distribution of cost of raw materials (fruits) based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	p
District of the unit	Alappuzha	402620.50	9289.5	02	3.63	0.458
	Ernakulam	6500529.63	1746109.962	08		
	Kozhikode	3928828.67	233359.1835	03		
No of products produced	< 3	967207.42	179442.9323	05	6.73**	0.002
	>=3	16880422.88	1200158.55	08		
Category	Vegetable	69933.53	1452.825	02	0.79*	0.025
	Fruit	8909574.87	323620.825	02		
	Both	8967162.53	717341.1794	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

* Significant at 0.05 level

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in Table 2 shows that the average amount used for fruit purchased is high in Ernakulam district (6500529.63) and low in Alappuzha district (402620.50). The amount used for fruit purchasing is high in units where three or more than three products are produced (16880422.88) and low in units that produce less than three product (967207.42). As the number of products producing increase the raw material used for producing the products also increases. The F test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=6.73).Units that producing both fruits & Vegetables products, have high average amount (8967162.53) and low in units that produce only vegetable products (69933.53). F test exhibit significant variation at 0.05 level (F=0.79).

3.2 COST OF RAW MATERIALS (VEGETABLES)

Table 3

Distribution of cost of raw materials (vegetables) based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	10478413.3	12747168.2	02	0.63	0.534
	Ernakulam	14659586.2	24377477.5	08		
	Kozhikode	7644816.3	34394910.9	03		
No of products produced	< 3	3609254.5	7492701.7	05	9.06**	0.000
	> =3	31268800.0	52620952.9	08		
Category	Vegetable	6309340.9	8963677.4	02	10.70**	0.000
	Fruit	1868333.3	4874435.8	02		
	Both	32802063.2	51759477.6	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in Table3 shows that District wise analysis, sample units in Ernakulam district purchased more vegetables (14659586.2) followed by Alappuzha district (10478413.3) and least in Kozhikode district (7644816.3). Average vegetable purchasing amount is high in sample units which produced more than three products (31268800.0) and low in units that produced less than three product (3609254.5). Sample units producing less than three product require only smaller amount of raw materials (vegetables) than units that are producing more products. At 0.01 level, F test have significant variation (F=9.06). Sample units that produce both fruits and vegetables products have high raw materials (vegetables) purchasing amount (32802063.2) and low is sample units that produce only fruit products. The F test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=10.70).

Table 4

Distribution of cost of raw materials (vegetables) based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	5138764.98	100441.675	02	3.14	0.534
	Ernakulam	7162203.97	430215.5601	08		
	Kozhikode	3767698.93	173585.641	03		
No of products produced	< 3	1825852.25	73431.70	05	6.74**	0.000
	> =3	16015021.98	908755.85	08		
Category	Vegetable	3194859.68	40189.225	02	187.01**	0.000
	Fruit	932237.48	1929.175	02		
	Both	15941394.80	656661.5988	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in Table 4 shows that District wise analysis, sample units in Ernakulam district purchased more vegetables (7162203.97) followed by Alappuzha district (5138764.98) and least in Kozhikode district (3767698.93). Average vegetable purchasing amount is high in sample units which produced more than three products (16015021.98) and low in units that produced less than three product (1825852.25). Sample units producing less than three product require only smaller amount of raw materials (vegetables) than units that are producing more products. At 0.01 level, F test have significant variation (F=6.74). Sample units that produce both fruits and vegetables products have high raw materials (vegetables) purchasing amount (15941394.80) and low is sample units that produce only fruit products. The F test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=187.01).

3.3 TOTAL COST OF RAW MATERIALS (FRUITS AND VEGETABLES)

Table 5

Distribution of total cost of raw materials (fruits and vegetables) based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	11330413.3	12408378.4	02	0.36	0.701
	Ernakulam	23176241.4	46442765.8	08		
	Kozhikode	20030898.0	50533573.2	03		
No of products produced	< 3	7493581.8	21509166.1	05	15.30**	0.000
	>= 3	63073168.4	77250560.7	08		
Category	Vegetable	6452113.6	8932303.8	02	6.91**	0.002
	Fruit	20449900.0	47987331.4	02		
	Both	48746905.3	68562755.4	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in Table 5 shows that District wise analysis, sample units in Ernakulam district purchased more (23176241.4) followed by Kozhikode district (20030898.0) and least in Alappuzha district (11330413.3). Sample units that are producing three or more than three products has the total cost high (63073168.4) and low in less than three product producing units. Significant variation $F=15.30$ is at 0.01 level. Units that produce three or more than three products procure more raw materials (fruits and vegetables) than less than three product producing units. Sample units that are producing both fruits and vegetables products have high total cost (48746905.3) followed by fruits products and vegetables products producing units. The test show significant variation at 0.01 level ($F=6.91$)

Table 6

Distribution of total cost of raw materials (fruits and vegetables) based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	417000.00	185000	02	2.36	0.458
	Ernakulam	6723003.73	5226652.385	08		
	Kozhikode	5516655.20	816496.58	03		
No of products produced	<3	1194315.80	109252.0023	05	6.58**	0.002
	>=3	16141868.40	2504464.763	08		
Category	Vegetable	78672.70	4100	02	1.21*	0.025
	Fruit	8167064.32	665000	02		
	Both	8916566.70	1133115.4	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

* Significant at 0.05 level

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in Table 6 shows that District wise analysis, sample units in Ernakulam district purchased more (6723003.73) followed by Kozhikode district (5516655.20) and least in Alappuzha district (417000.00). Sample units that are producing three or more than three products has the total cost high (16141868.40) and low in less than three product producing units. Significant variation $F= 6.58$ is at 0.01 level. Units that produce three or more than three products procure more raw materials (fruits and vegetables) than less than three product producing units. Sample units that are producing both fruits and vegetables products have high total cost (8916566.70) followed by fruits products and vegetables products producing units. The test show significant variation at 0.01 level ($F=1.21$)

3.4 LABOUR COST ANALYSIS

Labour cost is the second largest component in the cost structure of the fruit and vegetable processing industry. It includes all operating costs incurred in the conversion of raw material to finished products. The labour cost consists of direct wages paid to workers engaged in different processes of industry. It also include indirect wages given to store keeper and repair mechanics, other labour charges(fringe benefits) such as bonus, wages, leave with wages, E.P.F, gratuity to the workers etc. The labour engaged in fruit and vegetable processing units include permanent workers, technical workers and temporary workers. Permanent workers include male and female workers. Both workers have same scale of payment. Following table shows the wage payment of permanent workers of the sample units.

Table 7

Distribution of salary of permanent workers based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	332082	774922.8	02	0.12	0.888
	Ernakulam	369600	546721.2	08		
	Kozhikode	280551.6	624234	03		
No of products produced	< 3	133527.6	340940.4	05	12.93**	0.000
	>= 3	864000	958198.8	08		
Category	Vegetable	158727.6	337202.4	02	7.38**	0.001
	Fruit	288000	553527.6	02		
	Both	754105.2	919663.2	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in Table 7 shows that Salary to the permanent workers are found to be the districts wise analysis, Ernakulam district have high permanent labour cost (369600) and low in Kozhikode district (280551.6). Permanent labour cost is high in units that produce three or more than three products and low in units

that produce less than three product (133527.6). The permanent labour cost is high in units where both products are produce and low in units that produce only vegetables products (158727.6). The F test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=7.38).

Table 8

Distribution of salary of permanent workers based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	230489.00	19111	02	1.97	0.888
	Ernakulam	2300731.73	124317.97	08		
	Kozhikode	130974.98	2981149.8	03		
No of products produced	< 3	67803.48	26490.953	05	6.73**	0.000
	>=3	384629.60	12033.09	08		
Category	Vegetable	14091.50	416.5	02	68.31**	0.001
	Fruit	29416.10	8286.5	02		
	Both	386325.76	54075.06838	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in Table 8 shows that Salary to the permanent workers is found to be the districts wise analysis, Ernakulam district have high permanent labour cost (2300731.73). Permanent labour cost is high in units that produce three or more than three products and low in units that produce less than three product (67803.48). The permanent labour cost is high in units where both products are produce and low in units that produce only vegetables products (14091.50). The F test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=68.31).

3.5 REMUNERATION OF TEMPORARY WORKERS

Sample units not only employed permanent workers but also temporary workers. Wage payments relating to temporary workers of the sample units are presented in the table 9

Table 9

Distribution of salary of temporary workers based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	2759655.6	1855341.6	02	0.10	0.909
	Ernakulam	3629515.6	1921699.2	08		
	Kozhikode	2701900.7	2295696	03		
No of products produced	<3	2196714	1373199.6	05	17.91**	0.000
	>=3	4927552.8	2838874.8	08		
Category	Vegetable	2138113.2	1130379.6	02	9.84**	0.000
	Fruit	2900900.4	1876148.4	02		
	Both	4384250.4	2883757.2	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in Table 9 shows that in district wise analysis, Ernakulam district have high permanent labour cost (3629515.6) and low in Kozhikode district (2701900.7). Units that are producing three or more than three products has high temporary labour cost (4927552.8) and low in units that are producing less than three product (2196714). The F test show significant variation at number of products producing and category wise variable at 0.01 level F=17.91 and F= 9.84 respectively.

Table 10

Distribution of salary of temporary workers based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	1534587.50	28622.5	02	1.10	0.909
	Ernakulam	2164439.10	470027.7583	08		
	Kozhikode	1404381.93	217622.6312	03		
No of products produced	<3	1405322.80	72790.13265	05	5.85**	0.000
	>=3	2184882.55	304310.8721	08		
Category	Vegetable	1218121.20	25700	02	57.33**	0.000
	Fruit	2024528.40	18080	02		
	Both	4016470.96	54075.07	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in Table 10 shows that in district wise analysis, Ernakulam district have high permanent labour cost (2164439.10) and low in Kozhikode district (1404381.93). Units that are producing three or more than three products has high temporary labour cost (2184882.55) and low in units that are producing less than three product (1405322.80). Temporary labour cost is high in sample units that are producing both fruits and vegetables products (4016470.96) and low in units that produce only vegetable products (1218121.20). The F test show significant variation at number of products producing and category wise variable at 0.01 level F=5.85 and F= 57.33 respectively.

3.6 REMUNERATION OF TECHNICAL WORKERS

Technical workers are necessary for the units to check the quality of the products produced. Salary of technical workers based on the selected variables

Table 11

Comparison of salary of technical workers based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	p
District of the unit	Alappuzha	224000.4	542122.8	02	0.16	0.854
	Ernakulum	360000	795813.6	08		
	Kozhikode	330612	828906	03		
No of products produced	< 3	163636.8	552504	05	5.64**	0.005
	> =3	814736.4	1048869.6	08		
Category	Vegetable	160909.2	553214.4	02	3.39*	0.038
	Fruit	324000	767502	02		
	Both	694736.4	1051915.2	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

* Significant at 0.05 level

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in labour cost of technical staff in the sample units are displayed here. As per the table 11, Ernakulam district exhibit high technical labour cost (360000) followed by Kozhikode district (330612) and Alappuzha district (224000.4) Sample units that produce both products have high technical labour cost (694736.4) and low in units that produce only vegetable products (160909.2). The F test have variation at 0.05 level (F=3.39).

Table 12

Comparison of salary of technical workers based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	p
District of the unit	Alappuzha	115810.40	7500	02	3.85	0.854
	Ernakulam	287639.50	3260.15	08		
	Kozhikode	250374.00	53962.95	03		
No of products produced	< 3	84603.80	8516.07	05	6.68**	0.005
	> =3	507896.40	47458.22	08		
Category	Vegetable	77687.20	1070	02	8.49*	0.038
	Fruit	87705.00	21730	02		
	Both	343242.73	108327.53	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

* Significant at 0.05 level

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in labour cost of technical staff in the sample units are displayed here. As per the table 12, Technical labour cost is high in units, where three or more than three products are produced (507896.40) and low in units that produced less than three product (84603.80). The F test have significant variation at 0.01 level (F=6.68). Sample units that produce both products have high technical labour cost (343242.73) and low in units that produce only vegetable products (77687.20). The F test have variation at 0.05 level (F=8.49).

3.7 TOTAL LABOUR COST

Total labour cost consist of the amount paid to permanent, temporary and technical workers. The details of the same are shown below.

Table 13

Distribution of total labour cost based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	3315500.4	3076641.6	02	0.06	0.945
	Ernakulam	3592209.6	3056967.6	08		
	Kozhikode	3400206.6	3661518	03		
No of products produced	< 3	2493877.2	2135251.2	05	15.07**	0.000
	> =3	6606289.2	4636867.2	08		
Category	Vegetable	2457750	1868320.8	02	8.44**	0.000
	Fruit	3512900.4	3000417.6	02		
	Both	5833092	4686222	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in table 13 shows that district wise analysis of total labour cost exhibit that Ernakulam district have high total labour cost followed Kozhikode and finally the Alappuzha district (3315500.4). Units that produce three or more than three products have high labour cost, than less than three products producing units. F test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=15.07). Total labour cost is high in units that produce both products (5833092) and low in units that produce only vegetable products (2457750). The sample units that producing fruit products, vegetable products and both products producing units show significant difference at 0.01 level (F=8.44).

Table 14
Distribution of total labour cost based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	1428320.90	28510.5	02	2.04	0.945
	Ernakulam	1815189.60	99216.72276	08		
	Kozhikode	1605913.93	51096.85792	03		
No of products produced	< 3	1230396.20	37815.10809	05	6.76**	0.000
	> =3	3345711.70	55910.52422	08		
Category	Vegetable	957958.00	174500	02	26.55**	0.000
	Fruit	1277606.90	22731.5	02		
	Both	3033398.44	123702.26	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in table 14 shows that district wise analysis of total labour cost exhibit that Ernakulam district have high total labour cost followed Kozhikode and finally the Alappuzha district (1428320.90). Units that produce three or more than three products have high labour cost, than less than three products producing units. F test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=6.76). Total labour cost is high in units that produce both products (3033398.44) and low in units that produce only vegetable products (957958). The sample units that producing fruit products, vegetable products and both products producing units show significant difference at 0.01 level (F=26.55).

3.8 COST OF SERVICE

Cost of service includes electricity, water, communication, transportation, tax and license, insurance, stationary and postage and others. The items includes in the cost of service are shown in the table 15.

Total Cost of Service

Table 15

Distribution of total cost of service based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	p
District of the unit	Alappuzha	2497139.4	11288161.7	02	0.38	0.687
	Ernakulam	3803080.0	4454750.8	08		
	Kozhikode	2151163.4	4707626.6	03		
No of products Produced	< 3	1346739.8	3670574.9	05	6.62**	0.002
	> =3	6834517.9	10721201.1	08		
Category	Vegetable	1411679.8	3964903.8	02	5.33**	0.006
	Fruit	1903362.0	3045485.5	02		
	Both	6451315.8	10753814.3	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in table 15 shows that total cost of service of sample units exhibit significant difference at 0.01 level. Units that produce three or more than three products have high total cost of service (6834517.9) than less than three products producing units. Units that are producing both products have high total cost of service (6451315.8) and units that producing vegetable products (1411678.9) have least cost of service.

Table 16**Distribution of total cost of service based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19**

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	p
District of the unit	Alappuzha	1090292.78	28510.5	02	3.61	0.687
	Ernakulam	2015900.50	126019.2937	08		
	Kozhikode	889904.07	219910.2898	03		
No of products Produced	< 3	83258.80	37815.10809	05	6.77**	0.002
	> =3	3573940.40	55910.52422	08		
Category	Vegetable	667242.80	29855	02	144.30**	0.006
	Fruit	993068.50	2268.5	02		
	Both	3840511.13	269104.69	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in table 16 shows that total cost of service of sample units exhibit significant difference at 0.01 level. Units that produce three or more than three products have high total cost of service (3573940.40) than less than three products producing units. Units that are producing both products have high total cost of service (3840511.13) and units that producing vegetable products (667242.80) have least cost of service.

3.9 COST OF PACKING

Cost of packing includes the cost for bottles/jars, cartoons/wooden boxes, labels and others.

Details relating to the total cost of packing is shown in table

Total Cost of Packing

Details regarding the cost of packing before and after covid are shown below.

Table 17

Distribution of total cost of packing based on selected variables in food processing industry before Covid 19

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	775831.3	195313.5	02	1.70	0.498
	Ernakulum	1141234.1	138942.2	08		
	Kozhikode	954269.0	102265.5	03		
No of products Produced	< 3	665206.1	1004676.5	05	7.29**	0.001
	> =3	1883765.8	1980186.0	08		
Category	Vegetable	667746.3	981689.0	02	4.91**	0.009
	Fruit	776215.8	1034127.6	02		
	Both	1724118.4	1993652.4	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01

Food processing industry before Covid 19 mentioned in table 17, Among the district wise, Ernakulam district comes to first position [1141234.1], with Kozhikode district [954269] and Alappuzha district [775831.3] following. Sample units that produce three or more than three products have high cost of packing [1883765.8], compare to less than three products producing units [665206.1]. Significant variation can be seen at 0.01 level [F=4.91], where units that produce fruits and vegetables products. Total cost of packing is high in units that produce both products [1724118.4]

Table 18**Distribution of total cost of packing based on selected variables in food processing industry after Covid 19**

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	128651.80	11489.5	02	1.77	0.498
	Ernakulum	516172.38	112779.42	08		
	Kozhikode	346641.43	193908.57	03		
No of products Produced	< 3	401725.10	37815.10809	05	6.61**	0.001
	>=3	948188.30	78805.84825	08		
Category	Vegetable	717242.80	79855	02	34.90**	0.009
	Fruit	978068.50	12731.5	02		
	Both	2996066.69	431035.8231	09		

Source : Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01

Food processing industry after Covid 19 mentioned in table 18, among the district wise, Ernakulam district comes to first position [516172.38], with Kozhikode district [346641.43] and Alappuzha district [128651.80] following. Sample units that produce three or more than three products have high cost of packing [948188.30], compare to less than three products producing units [401725.10]. Significant variation can be seen at 0.01 level [F= 6.61], where units that produce fruits and vegetables products. Total cost of packing is high in units that produce both products [2996066.69].

3.10 PROBLEMS RELATING TO RAW MATERIALS

The major problems relating to the raw materials faced by the sample units are.

1. High price of raw materials
2. Low quality of raw materials
3. Shortage of raw materials
4. Lack of preservation
5. Seasonal nature
6. Delay of raw materials

A ranking method is used to know the relative importance of the problems of raw material. The result is shown below.

Table 19

Distribution ranking of raw material problems

	Mean	Rank
High price	3.4	4
Low quality	3.9	2
Shortage	4.1	1
Lack of preservation	3.6	3
Seasonal nature	3.3	5
Decay	2.7	6

Source: Primary Data

The table 19 shows that from the various factors, shortage of raw material is the prime factor followed by low quality of raw materials, the third position is occupied by lack of preservation of raw material, then high price of raw material again hit capacity utilization of raw materials. Seasonal nature of raw material and Decay nature of fruit and vegetables occupy fifth and sixth position respectively.

3.11 PROBLEMS RELATING TO LABOUR

Major problems of labour related to sample units were identified as

1. Absenteeism
2. Strike
3. Lack of skilled labour
4. Labour turnover
5. Lack of training facility and
6. High remuneration

Ranking of the reasons of the labour of selected sample units are as follows.

Table 20

Distribution of ranking of labour problems

	Mean	Rank
Absenteeism	2.7	5
Strike	1.6	6
Lack of skilled workers	5.4	1
Labour turnover	4.4	2
Lack of training facility	3.3	4
High remuneration	3.5	3

Source: Primary Data

Table 20, clearly exhibits the ranking of under capacity utilization of labour of the sample units. The main reason of under capacity utilization of labour is lack of skilled labour ranked as first, second position goes to labour turnover, followed by high remuneration, fourth rank goes to lack of training facility, fifth position to absenteeism and final position to strike of the labour.

B. PROFIBILITY

Profit is the excess of the sales revenue earned over the cost of production incurred. In other words, profit is measured as excess of output values over the input costs. Profitability is a relative concept showing the ability of the firm to make profit. For measuring the profitability of a concern profit is to be related to sales or capital. Profit when related to sales is called profit margin. The economic viability and an industry can be assessed from its profitability. Profitability ratios are calculated to measure the overall efficiency of the business. In other words, they are the ratios, which reveal the total effects of the business transactions on the profit position of enterprises and indicate how far the enterprise has been successful in its aim.

The profitability ratios used to study the profit earning capacity of the fruit and vegetable processing units under study.

- (1) Gross profit ratio
- (2) Net Profit Ratio
- (3) Return on investment
- (4) Profit Volume Ratio

3.12 GROSS PROFIT RATIO

Gross profit ratio is the ratio which expresses the relationship between gross profit and sales.

$$\text{Gross profit ratio} = \frac{\text{Sales}}{\text{Gross profit}} \times 100$$

Higher the ratios better the result. The post Covid gross profit ratio of the sample units are given to table 21.

Table 21

Distribution of gross profit ratio based on selected variables

Variables		Mean		SD		P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	21.5	.005	2	6.37	0.242
	Ernakulam	20.45	.23	8		
	Kozhikode	18.65	.008	3		
No. of products	<3	19.85	0.014	5		
	>=3	19.35	0.023	8		
Category	Vegetable	19.35	0.005	2	0.43	0.519
	Fruit	20.65	0.005	2		
	Both	20.68	0.326	9		

Source: Primary Data

Table 21 displays that gross profit ratio found to be high in Alappuzha District (21.5), units that producing more than 3 products (19.85) and both products producing units (20.68) during the post Covid period.

3.13 NET PROFIT RATIO

Net profit ratio indicates the efficiency of management in manufacturing, selling administration and other activities of the firm. This ratio is the overall measure of the profitability of the firm. This ratio indicates the quantum of profit earned by a concern high net profit ratio indicates that the profitability of the concern is good. This ratio indicates firms capacity to face adverse economic conditions, such as price competition, low demand etc. This ratio is expressed as a percentage and is calculated as follows. Table 22 shows the post Covid net profit ratio of the sample units based on selected variables

$$\text{Net profit ratio} = \frac{\text{Sales}}{\text{Net profit}} \times 100$$

Table 22

Distribution of net profit ratio based on selected variables

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	8.55	0.05	2	1.13	0.224
	Ernakulam	7.80	0.36	8		
	Kozhikode	6.50	0.08	3		
No of product s produced	<3	7.29	0.03	5	6.75	0.068
	>=3	8.21	0.04	8		
Category	Vegetable	10.65	3.00	2	0.33	0.644
	Fruit	9.25	1.05	2		
	Both	10.26	0.43	9		

Source: Primary Data

The average net profit ratio is high in Alappuzha district (8.55) followed by Ernakulam district (7.80) and least among Kozhikode district (6.50). The Statistics show that the variation on the net profit ratio among the industries in the three districts is not significant. The average net profit ratio is high in the sample units where less than three products are produced. (8.21). The average net profit ratio is high in the sample units where both fruit and vegetables used to make products (10.21). The average net profit of the sample units shows that there is no significant variation

3.14 RETURN ON INVESTMENT

The profitability ratios can be computed by relating the profit of a firm to its investments. Profit is only a narrow measure for evaluating the performance of a business unit. ROI is one of the most important ratio used for measuring the overall efficiency of a firm. Profit is only a narrow measure for evaluating the performance of a business unit. ROI is one of the most important ratio used for measuring the overall efficiency of a firm. As the primary objective of a business is to maximize its earnings, this ratio indicates the extent to which the primary objective of the business is being achieved. As the ratio reveals how well the resources of a unit are being used, higher the ratio better the results. ROI establishes the relationship between the profit earned and capital employed.

Table 23

Distribution of return on investment based on selected variable

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	0.15	0.01	2	3.75	0.179
	Ernakulam	6.45	0.02	8		
	Kozhikode	2.60	0.08	3		
No of product s produced	<3	7.48	0.22	8	6.76	0.284
	>=3	2.45	0.01	5		
Category	Vegetable	1.50	0.05	2	3.39	0.156
	Fruit	5.80	0.10	2		
	Both	7.62	0.07	9		

Source: Primary Data

Return on investment is high in Ernakulam district (6.45) and low in Alappuzha district (0.15). The average return on investment does not show any significant variation. It means that district have no influence on the return on investment. As the number of product increase return on investment also increases. The sample units which produce three or more than three products have high return on investment (7.48). Sample units that produce both fruits and vegetable products have high return on investment (7.62) than fruits products producing units (5.80) and vegetable products producing (1.50).

3.15 PROFIT VOLUME RATIO

Profit volume ratio is the relation between contribution and sales expressed as a percentage indicating the intrinsic strength of a product which denotes as to what is the contribution from sales revenue of each rupee. It measures the overall efficiency of production, administration, selling, financing, pricing and tax management. This ratio is different from gross profit ratio and net profit ratio. The gross profit ratio shows the margin left after meeting the manufacturing costs and it measures the efficiency of production as well as pricing. The net profit ratio shows the earnings left for the shareholders as a percentage of net sales. A high P/V Ratio indicates that a slight increase in sales without increase in fixed costs will result in higher profits. A low P/V ratio which indicates low profitability can be improved by increasing selling price, reducing marginal costs or selling products having high P/V ratio. It is calculated as under:

$$(\text{Contribution} * 100) / \text{Sales}$$

Contribution:

It is the difference between sales revenue and variable cost. Higher contribution is treated as a profitable situation. Contribution is calculated as contribution = sales - variable cost

The post Covid profit volume ratio of the sample units is presented in table 24

Table 24

Distribution of profit volume ratio based on selected variables

Variables		Mean	SD	N	F	P
District of the unit	Alappuzha	38.20	0.05	2	1.52	0.997
	Ernakulam	38.60	0.36	8		
	Kozhikode	38.15	0.08	3		
No of product produced	<3	37.45	0.04	5	6.75	0.228
	>=3	39.00	0.09	8		
Category	Vegetable	38.45	0.04	5	6.75	0.795
	Fruit	39.00	0.09	8		
	Both	37.45	0.04	5		

Source : Primary Data

Profit volume ratio is high in Ernakulam district (38.60) and low in Kozhikode district (38.15). There is a slight difference in the profit volume ratio of the sample unit. Sample units that produce less than three products have high profit volume ratio (39). Sample units that produce products of fruits have high p/v ratio (39) followed by vegetable products (38.45) and both fruit and vegetable products(37.45). In short, category does not influence the p/v ratio of the sample units.

CHAPTER IV

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The analysis shows that impact of food processing industries before Covid 19 and after Covid 19 can be traced. State has an abundant supply of fruits and vegetables. Due to the seasonal nature of fruits and vegetables, most of them naturally leads to wastage. To prevent the wastages, processing of fruits and vegetables started. Processing units not only contributes to the food requirements but also significant role in the economy of the state. It is in this background that the present study is undertaken with the following objectives.

1. To study the cost structure of FPIs.
2. To study the profitability analysis of FPIs.
3. To study the production problems faced by FPIs

Pretested interview schedule was used for collecting the primary data, in order to carry out the study with above stated objectives. Analysis are based on District, number of products produced and category wise. Certain mathematical and statistical tools were used to reach meaningful conclusions. Following are the summary of findings emerged from the study.

4.1 COST STRUCTURE

- Variable Costs consist of material cost, labour cost, cost of packing and cost of services. Materials contain fruit and vegetables.
- ❖ Before Covid-19 Market value of fruit found to be high in Ernakulam district (12386081.6), units that producing three or more than three products (31804368.4) and both fruit and vegetable products producing units (18581566.7).
- ❖ After Covid-19 Market value of fruit found to be high in Ernakulam district (6500529.63), units that producing three or more than three products (16880422.88) and both fruit and vegetable products producing units (8967162.53).

- ❖ Before Covid-19 Market value of vegetable found to be high in Ernakulam district (14659586.2) units that produce three or more than three products and units that produce both fruit and vegetable products.
- ❖ After Covid-19 Market value of vegetable found to be high in Ernakulam district (7162203.97) units that produce three or more than three products and units that produce both fruit and vegetable products.

4.2 LABOUR COST

- Labour cost consists of wages for permanent, temporary and technical workers salary of permanent workers found to be high in Kozhikode district, units that producing three or more than three products and units producing both fruit and vegetable products.
- ❖ Before Covid-19 Wages of temporary workers found to be high in large Ernakulam district (3629515.6), units that produce three or more than three products (4927552.8) and units that produce both products (4384250.4).
- ❖ After Covid-19 Wages of temporary workers found to be high in large Ernakulam district (2164439.10), units that produce three or more than three products (2184882.55) and units that produce both products (4016470.96).
- ❖ Before Covid-19 Wages of technical workers found to be high in Ernakulam district (360000), units that produce three or more than three products (814736.4) and units that produce both products (694736.4).
- ❖ After Covid-19 Wages of technical workers found to be high in Ernakulam district (287639.50), units that produce three or more than three products (507896.40) and units that produce both products (343242.73).

4.3 COST OF SERVICE

- ❖ Before Covid-19 Components of cost of service are electricity, water, communication, tax and license, insurance, stationary and postage, and others. Cost of services found to be high in Ernakulam district (3803080.0), three or more than three products producing units (6834517.9) and both products producing units (6451315.8). F test

exhibit significant variation in number of products produced and category wise classification.

- ❖ After Covid-19 Components of cost of service are electricity, water, communication, tax and license, insurance, stationery and postage, and others. Cost of services found to be high in Ernakulam district (2015900.50), three or more than three products producing units (3573940.40) and both products producing units (3840511.13). F test exhibit significant variation in number of products produced and category wise classification.

4.4 COST OF PACKING

- ❖ Before Covid-19 It includes the cost for bottle/ jar, cartoons/ wooden boxes, labels and others. Total cost of packing found to be high in Ernakulum district (516172.38), three or more than three products producing units and units that produce both products (1724118.4).
- ❖ After Covid-19 It includes the cost for bottle/ jar, cartoons/ wooden boxes, labels and others. Total cost of packing found to be high in Ernakulum district (1141234.1), three or more than three products producing units and units that produce both products (2996066.69).

4.5 PROFITABILITY

- ❖ Gross profit ratio found to be high in, Alappuzha district (21.15) units that producing more than three products (19.85) and units that producing both products (20.68). Significant difference does not exist among variables.
- ❖ Net profit ratio found to be high in, Alappuzha district (8.55) units that produce less than three products (8.31) and vegetable products producing units (10.65).
- ❖ Return on Investment found to be high in Ernakulam district (6.45), units that producing more than three products (7.48) and units that producing both products (7.62).
- ❖ P/v ratio found to be high in Ernakulam district (38.60), units that producing less than three products and units that producing fruit products.

4.6 CONCLUSION

The impact of food processing industries before Covid 19 and after Covid 19. In Kerala fruit and vegetable processing industry mainly classified as large scale sector, small scale sector, home scale sector and cottage sector. fruit and vegetable processing industry in Kerala. Units that situated in Alappuzha, Ernakulam, Kozhikode districts were selected for study. The other variables used for the study were number of products produced and category wise classification.

The finding shows that Cost structure of fruit and vegetable processing units of food processing industries before Covid 19 and after Covid 19 in Kerala state found to be high in units that producing three or more than three products and both fruit and vegetable products producing units. Main production problem associate with raw material and labour are unavailability of raw materials and lack of skilled labour.

The impact of food processing industries before Covid 19 and after Covid 19 also affected Working capital turnover ratio found to be efficient in units that producing three or more than three products, both fruit and vegetable products producing units. Fixed asset turnover ratio showed best in large scale sector, units producing more than three products, both fruit and vegetable products producing units. Both are suffered from the main problem non willingness of bank to financial assistance.

The ongoing global pandemic has left no sector untouched by its wave of impacts. While the number of people being affected by Covid-19 still continues to climb, it is needless to comprehend the pandemics grave impacts on every corner of the nation's economy. With almost all the segments having fallen prey to the uncertain impacts of Covid-19, even the food and beverage industry in India is responding to the ongoing crisis by bracing itself for Corona virus impacts.

4.7 SUGGESTIONS

To improve the prospects of the processing industry, following suggestion can be made on the basis of findings.

1. Shortage of raw materials occurs due to the seasonal nature of fruit and vegetable. Hence proper storage facilities should be introduced. Every units are not in a position

to arrange facilities for storage, so government should take necessary arrangement to overcome this hurdle. Maintain cold storage facilities at district level. Though the sample units of Kerala depend upon other states for raw materials, quality and price may be varying.

2. Co-operative societies may be started at the panchayat and district level for buying and selling of the fruits and vegetable that grown in our state. Vegetable and fruit promotion council, and department of agriculture should provide various scheme and subsidy to the farmers for encouraging fruit and vegetable cultivation.
3. Farmers should give proper information and training regarding the quality, hygienic and sanitary practice of farming. Government should setup centralized agencies to look after the procuring, storage and distribution of raw materials. KINFRA were started in various districts which help to overcome certain infra structure difficulties faced by the units. But units are scattered along the 14 districts of Kerala, only few enjoyed the facilities provide by the KINFRA. So mini KINFRA can be started in the district were the concentration of units high.
4. Lack of skilled labour may lead huge financial constrain to units. proper training facility should be given to the workers before they were employed in the units. Establishment of technical institution should be done. Labour should be under go alternate training, in order to aware about the changes that took place in world.

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EXPORT ANALYSIS OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PROCESSING UNITS

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Abstract

India is the world's second largest producers of fruit and vegetables. People generally prefer fresh fruits and vegetables due to availability of seasonal fruits and vegetables through out the year available at low price. Due to the lack of proper harvesting, processing and storage facilities there should be an estimated loss of 20-35% which is valued at Rs 50,000 crores annually. In most countries, the production of perishable food crop is seasonal and available only for a short period. During this time, the large quantity of food can be absorbed by the market. Hence the remain will lead to spoilage. So we have to preserve and process the food not only to avoid wastage of food but also gain in the income of growers.

Keywords: Export, processing units.

Introduction

Only 2% of fruits and vegetables are processed into value added products. Hence there should be maximum utilization of fruits and vegetable is a must. The largest segment in processed products are ready to serve beverages followed by fruit pulp, pickles, Chutneys, jams, squashes, syrup etc. Food processing sector is highly fragmented industry it widely comprises of the following sub segments fruit and vegetable, milk and milk products, meat and poultry, marine products, grain processing, packaged or convenience food and packaged drinks. There are about 25% of fruits and vegetable units in organized sector. At present food processing sector employs 13 million people directly and about 35 million people indirectly. Food processing sector contributed over 14% of manufacturing GDP with a share of Rs 2, 80,000 crores of this in the unorganized sector accounted for more than 70% of production in terms of volume and 50% in terms of value.

Export of Fruits and Vegetables

Vast production of fruits and vegetables offers great opportunities for export. In 2018-19 the country's export of fruits and vegetables have crossed Rs 5956.72 crores which comprised of fruits worth Rs 3573.75 crores and vegetables worth Rs 3586.97 crores. Some items of export are onion, walnut, mango, banana, grapes, okra, potatoes, chilies, bitter gourd, green peas etc.

The main fruits that enter into export market are mangoes, grapes, citrus, banana, letches etc. The main destination for export of fruits are Middle East, United Kingdom, Europe and to some extent Singapore, Malaysia etc. The important vegetable exported are potatoes, Onion, Peas, cabbage etc.

Table 1
Distribution of Export of Fruits and Vegetables from India 2016-17 to 2020-21.

Product	2016-17		2017-18		2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)								
Onions	1008606.48	103577.89	1670186.9	182752.21	1664922.39	231942.98	1182324.20	177928.62	1309924.82	172299.80
Other vegetables	350235.47	48949.01	505285.46	68020.32	419241.35	73185.90	494754.60	90975.88	729810.62	129893.77
Walnut	6716.48	16207.80	5696.34	14123.63	9073.38	19789.51	5762.34	16629.25	5841.56	23108.40
Mangoes	54350.80	12741.76	83703.18	17071.25	74460.61	20053.98	58863.41	16483.60	63441.29	20974.30
Grapes	96963.57	31782.51	124627.97	40861.28	131153.61	54533.89	98005.12	42830.28	108584.56	60288.15
Other fruits	207700.78	30452.60	256768.53	43086.84	260675.43	52283.32	254899.24	49597.86	108584.56	60288.15
Total	1724573.58	243711.57	2646267.77	365915.53	2559526.77	451789.58	2094608.91	394445.49	2488950.67	480150.62

Source: Compiled from the Annual report of various years, Agricultural processed export development authority

As per the table, onion is the major item that is exported from India. During 2017-18 quantity of export of onion was found to be high. While the value of export of onion found to be high in 2018-19. Like wise quantity of export of other vegetables also found to be high in 2017-18. In 2020-21, value of export of vegetable from India was 302193.57 lakhs. In 2020-21 grapes and other fruits are exported from India in same quantity and value. The quantity and value of export of processed fruits and vegetables is given in the table.

Table 2
Distribution of export of processed fruits and Vegetables

Products	2016-17		2017-18		2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
	qty (MT)	Value (Lakhs)								
Dried and Preserved vegetable	125726.28	42993.81	147861.22	49641.51	124613.50	53207.48	108486.85	50173.58	138464.03	70018.80
Mango pulp	166752.17	50968.51	173013.60	75298.90	186197.85	74460.77	170219.72	81893.27	150499.06	62082.91
Other processed F & V	311756.29	96281.65	387126.42	137179	397978.17	43550.63	349498.25	137282.60	459514.68	211785.85

Source: Compiled from the Annual report of various years, Agricultural processed export development authority

Table 2 showed the export of processed fruits and vegetable products of India. India export 138464.03 MT of dried and preserved vegetable products, 150499.06 mango pulp and 459514.68 MT of other processed fruits and vegetables in 2020-21. Among them, value of other processed fruits and vegetables are found to be high.

The major destination of export of Indian fruits and vegetables are U.A.E, Saudi Arabia, Nepal, Malaysia, Bangladesh, UK, Netherland, Pakistan and Sri Lanka. Data relating to export from India to various countries are shown below in the table 2.

Table 3
Export from India to Countries in the World 2016-21

Sl.No	Country	2016-17		2017-18		2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
		Qty (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Qty (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Qty (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Qty (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Qty (MT)	Value (Lakhs)
1.	U.A.E	250591.1	28833.68	340607.66	48532.74	335027.01	62236.08	347987.05	66034.69	353157.52	59585.51
2.	Saudi Arabia	96890.99	25212.39	115126.71	37566.17	128161.02	43174.45	113138.05	42076.97	132489.55	49021.16
3.	Malaysia	301313.84	441344.78	286228.23	32803.74	303137.82	41329.53	295577.92	51078.02	301313.84	44344.78
4.	Bangladesh	3697852.54	60725.98	871577.81	94622.23	958718.42	135712.41	560161.4	80531.98	465855.05	81112.11
5.	United States	72315.67	24404.8	107739.53	42578.18	99583.7	40710.1	89332.46	35942.27	106272.18	53789.69
6.	U.K	55306.12	22437.72	65479.15	27880.48	166256.64	33764.72	63563.21	30534.69	67476.14	39391.32
7.	France	24330.45	8377.41	37589.9	13674.97	14656.62	11030.75	24444.46	8573.87	31985.42	13463.15
8.	Kuwait	18342.44	4800.06	40995.34	7604.39	909051.25	123454.1	48446.33	11462.5	5728.6	2563.17
9.	Italy	3702.81	659.94	3799.15	1177.081	5927.41	1961.16	7364.78	1505.83	3435.21	2006.71
10.	Canada	23772.68	41323.28	30693.15	9021.64	34034.7	12173.92	25334.49	14102.09	24563.43	9946.23
11.	Japan	9549.91	5832.86	8079.55	5795.5	5439.11	3759.02	6654.2	4503.22	8110.59	6434.98
12.	Switzerland	889.42	1176.78	942.03	932.07	1116.1	1226	1125.41	1759.62	1304.62	2916.21

13.	Australia	12807.83	3993.7	15024.15	4992.9	18961.77	7328.02	18628.82	6553.7	20051.4	8022.34
14.	China	4372.94	905.92	877.75	497.19	3022.35	1788.11	2080.12	1396.61	4809.12	2789.12
15.	Germany	28592.06	9579.92	18690.6	7867.88	19990.46	9944.55	17038.5	11050.28	19030.31	13653.98
16.	New Zealand	2275.84	797.06	2931.81	1129.81	3215.66	1240.07	3277.78	1162.51	3613.85	1334.43
17.	Philippines	10539.3	1065.76	34132.93	4922.47	11909.61	3744.89	3551.53	1775.81	3181.21	2038.28
18.	Zimbabwe	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.80	0.34	0.90	0.66
19.	Mauritius	15248.12	2408.88	14862.81	2233.03	14223.59	14061.65	12647.66	2270.44	15684.03	2908.62
20.	Iran	2618.51	1094.69	3527.45	2146.35	21112.48	5727.71	15801.44	6552.9	10111.26	6569.65

Source: Compiled from the Annual report of various years, Directorate general of commercial intelligence and statistics

As per the table 3, main export destination of fruits and vegetables from India are shown. In 2020-21, India exported 465855.05 MT of fruits and vegetables to Bangladesh and next position occupies by 353137.52 MT of fruits and vegetables by UAE. According to the table 3, Zimbabwe have the least amount of export from India i.e., 0.90 MT of fruits and vegetables.

Export of fruits and vegetables to developed countries.

India export fruits and vegetables and its products to various parts of the world. The main items for export include fresh onions, fresh fruits and vegetables, fresh mangoes, other processed fruits and vegetables etc.

Table 4
Export of fruits and vegetables from India to Developed Countries

Product Name	2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)
Other processed fruits and vegetables	240069.39	94089.50	219730.78	87840.34	271706.76	128756.12
Dried and preserved vegetables	94726.47	39691.24	67234.65	31565.40	87083.23	48011.10
Fresh grapes	52540.54	30160.06	31903.76	22691.43	32882.32	24685.34
Mango Pulp	43112.57	23634.59	51500.43	28850.67	42411.39	24113.32
Other fresh vegetables	38528.11	15384.56	38070.04	15662.10	47969.47	21961.02
Other fresh fruits	19213.72	9093.12	13865.50	6646.05	14037.09	7052.92
Fruit and Vegetable seeds	706.38	5349.22	978.21	5270.19	1374.29	8204.12
Fresh onions	41840.08	6031.01	32930.07	4692.14	48180.88	6313.04
Fresh mangoes	4595.33	2809.41	4167.54	2204.89	4739.64	2885.04
Total	535332.59	226242.71	460380.98	205423.21	550385.07	271982.02

Source : Compiled from the Annual report of various years Directorate general of commercial intelligence and statistics

As per the table 3.8, 535332.59 MT of fruits and vegetables and its products are exported from India to the Developed countries in 2018-19. In 2019-20 there is decrease in the quantity of export. Again there is a hike of export of fruits and vegetables and its products from India to the Developed countries in 2020-21 i.e., 550385.07 MT. Among the items, dried and preserved vegetables have the export quantity high (87083.23 MT).

Export of fruit and vegetable processing to developing economies

India export fruits and vegetables and its products not only to developed countries but also to developing and least developing countries. Data relating to these are shown below.

Table 5
Export of fruits and vegetables and its products from India to Developing Countries

Product Name Items	2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)
Other processed fruits and vegetables	145823.32	45923.55	121011.28	45896.23	171685.20	77165.55
Dried and preserved vegetables	27610.78	12537.83	33456.04	16579.21	38810.59	18349.88
Fresh grapes	28234.47	17512.24	22814.64	14009.34	30999.80	22040.51
Mango Pulp	133904.15	47216.12	109185.80	48989.56	101281.89	35371.74
Other fresh vegetables	241839.48	46037.87	286878.77	61395.42	479843.10	93149.80
Other fresh fruits	144358.80	33422.33	14910.59	30878.26	139477.45	36552.63
Fruit and Vegetable seeds	6284.58	7561.63	8032.57	10276.58	8091.88	16618.11
Fresh onions	819735.00	110077.97	727428.86	113399.33	913016.79	122986.08
Fresh mangoes	32252.99	13567.82	29654.92	12209.70	27172.85	13357.69
Total	1580043.57	333857.36	1353373.47	353633.63	1910379.55	435591.99

Source Compiled from the Annual report of various years Directorate general of commercial intelligence and statistics

As per the table 5, 1910379.55 Mt of fruits and vegetables and its products are exported to the developing countries from India in 2020-21. Like wise in the above table 5, quantity of export in 2018- 19 was 158004.57 MT there was decrease in 2019-20 and again increase in 2020-21. Among the items, fresh onions are exported in large quantity to the developing countries from India in 2020-21. The next position occupied by the fresh vegetables i.e., 479843.10 MT.

Table 6
Export of fruits and vegetables and its products from India to least Developing Countries

Product Name	2018-19		2019-20		2020-21	
	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)	Quantity (MT)t	Value (Lakhs)	Quantity (MT)	Value (Lakhs)
Other processed fruits and vegetables	11534.77	3370.59	7534.12	3243.45	13839.52	5143.45
Dried and preserved vegetables	1861.94	690.35	7250.01	1735.65	11989.70	3233.03
Fresh grapes	50244.92	6839.79	43234.79	6109.95	44548.51	13463.21
Mango Pulp	5095.19	2098.13	5140.98	2063.89	3488.63	1370.60
Other fresh vegetables	138743.88	11713.99	169749.00	13896.34	200928.58	14710.49
Other fresh fruits	97043.31	9746.15	99095.64	12055.75	116967.42	29708.00
Fruit and Vegetable seeds	1892.14	1590.17	2611.66	2942.76	5139.45	3927.95
Fresh onions	803289.21	115820.86	421919.64	59826.96	348603.57	42974.75
Fresh mangoes	37611.39	3675.71	25040.94	2069.01	31525.22	4730.33
Total	1147316.75	155545.74	781576.78	103943.76	777030.6	119261.81

Source : Compiled from the Annual report of various years, Directorate general of commercial intelligence and statistics

Table 6 displays, Export of fruits and vegetables and its products from India to least Developing Countries. During 2020-21 777030.6 MT of products are exported from India. Among them, fresh onions and fresh mangoes occupies first and second position of items that was exported from India and last position was occupied by the mango pulp I e., 3488.63 MT.

CONCLUSION

Lack of transport infrastructures to link the production pocket areas, particularly in the hills and mountains. Very few collection centers and the limited centers are not well organized. Lack of cold warehouses. Bumper crops often results losses to the farmers, due to sharp decline in prices. Poor post harvest operations, substantial losses during transportation, poor storage, grading and sorting etc. Inadequate development of vegetable and fruit based industries, poor. value added activities of the products.

LABOUR COST ANALYSIS OF FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KERALA

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ABSTRACT

Kerala is considered by several substantial socio-economic, industrial, and political individualities. Kerala offers a conducive environment for setting up any industry. Protruding sectors in Kerala are information technology, tourism, and agro-based business including food processing, readymade garments, mining, ayurvedic medicines, etc. The key sectors that contribute to the GDP of the state are rubber, coir tourism, food processing, and chemicals and fertilizers. As of 2019, there are 1774 food processing units in Kerala. It provides 35 percent of revenue from export. The food processing sector gains Rs. 9000 crores from export and has a potential to become Rs. 50,000 crores worth of industry. The food processing industry is significant to the Kerala economy on account of its influence on food requirements. The food processing industry provides employment opportunities and is highly labour intensive which is suitable for organised on a home scale itself. The importance of this sector is further enhanced by the fact that 70 percent of the population depends upon agricultural activities for livelihood. Kerala is consecrated with natural resources. Kerala has several fruits and Vegetables which are seasonal. In specific seasons there is an abundant supply of fruits and vegetables but in other seasons, there is a glaring scarcity. There is a wide gap between the availability and requirement of fruits and vegetables in the state. Kerala is considered a consumer-based state, dependent upon neighboring states for the food requirement, it is very unfortunate. Here comes the requirement of processing.

Keywords: Food processing sector, large scale sector, small scale sector, home-scale sector, cottage sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

Food processing is defined as that branch of manufacturing that starts with raw animal, vegetable, or marine materials and transform them into intermediate, foodstuff, or edible products through an application of labour, machinery, energy, and scientific knowledge. Food processing in India was started as a family profession. Despite the lack of training, they prepared quality foods like pickles, papads, fried, roasted, and puffed cereals for local consumption. The organized food industry was started by British officers and settlers. During the Second World War, the number of this unit was multiplied to satisfy the needs of troops. The products produced at those times were bread, biscuits, jams, squashes, syrups, and fruit. It is not possible to acquire adequate growth in agro-hortic. The growth in agricultural and horticultural production improved the quality of raw materials both qualitatively and quantitatively, resulting in the opening of many new local and multinational companies in the field of food processing.

India is the second-largest food-producing country next to China. The food processing industry is one of the largest industries in India. It ranked fifth in terms of production, consumption, export, and expected growth. The Indian food market is estimated to be in the order of Rs 1,85,000 crores, of this semi-processed food accounts for about 25% and processed food about 17%, and the remaining 75% is the fresh food market. The food processing industry employs about 16 lakh workers. The turnover of this industry is estimated to be Rs1,44,000 crores of which Rs 111.200 crores from the unorganized sector in 2017. The agriculture sector without establishing well-organized facilities was identified only during the eighties. India is an agriculture-based country. Lots of fruits and vegetables are grown in different parts of the country. In India, the fruits have been given an important place as it is offered to God at every important festival, and have also been mentioned in the epics like Mahabharata, Ramayana, and the writings of Sushrutha and Charaka.⁴⁴ During 2019-20 India's fruit production is 96.424 million MT and occupies 8% of the world's fruit production, India is the second-largest producer of vegetables and accounts for 15% of the world's vegetable production. India's vegetable production is 176.33 million MT. The major Indian-produced fruits are Mango, Banana, citrus, fruits, apple, guava, papaya, pineapple grapes, and major vegetables are Potato, onion, tomato, cabbage, and Cauliflower.

Processing fruits and vegetables require a workforce. The workforce includes all operating costs necessary to carry out the raw form into finished form. It consists of permanent workers, temporary workers, and technical workers.

2. METHODOLOGY

A stratified Random sampling technique was used to carry out the study. In the first stage based on the geographical, cultural, and social environments the state of Kerala was divided into 3 regions, viz., the Southern region, Central region, and Northern region. The fruit and vegetable units operating in the state of Kerala are functioning under 4 divisions viz., large scale sector, small scale sector, cottage sector, and home-scale sector. One district from each region having all the 4 types of fruit and vegetable processing units was selected on a random base. Details regarding the cost of the workforce are given below.

3. LABOUR COST ANALYSIS

Labour cost is the second-largest component in the cost structure of the fruit and vegetable processing industry. It includes all operating costs incurred in the conversion of raw materials to finished products. Wages can be defined as the compensation, usually financial, received by the workers in exchange for their labour. The labour cost consists of direct wages paid to workers engaged in different processes of industry. It also includes indirect wages given to storekeepers and repair mechanics, other labour charges (fringe benefits) such as bonuses, wages, leaves with wages, E.P.F, gratuity to the workers, etc. The labour engaged in fruit and vegetable processing units include permanent workers, technical workers, and temporary workers. Permanent workers include male and female workers. Both workers have the same scale of payment. The following table shows the wage payment of permanent workers of the sample units.

Table 1 Distribution of salary of permanent workers based on selected variables

		Mean	SD	N	F	P
Sector	Large scale sector	2055999.6	480450	9	355.29**	0.000
	Home scale sector	30856.8	36284.4	28		
	Small scale sector	325564.8	140470.8	23		
	Cottage sector	93818.4	94366.8	33		

Salary to the permanent workers is found to be high in large-scale units (2055999.6) followed by small scale sector (325564.8), cottage sector (93818.4), and home-scale sector (30856.8). The F test shows variation at a 0.01 level (F=355.29). As the size of the sector increases, more workers are necessary to meet the ends. Scheffe multiple comparisons examine the result on a pair basis and are presented below.

Table 2 Scheffe multiple comparisons of salary of permanent workers based on selected variables

		Pair	F'	Sig.
Sector	Large scale sector (A)	A & B	318.56**	0.00
	Home scale sector (B)	A & C	220.91**	0.00
	Small scale sector (C)	A & D	310.51**	0.00
	Cottage sector (D)	B & C	12.51**	0.00
		B & D	0.68	0.56
		C & D	8.3**	0.00

Source: Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Scheffe multiple comparisons show that large scale sector with home-scale sector(318.56), large scale with small scale (F=220.91), and large scale with cottage sector also have significant variation at 0.01 level. Significant variation exists between the home scale sector with small scale sector [F=12.51] and small scale sector with cottage sector at 0.01 level (F=8.3). Large scale and small scale require more permanent workers than other sectors. Differences exist in the wage payment of permanent workers among sectors.

3.1 Remuneration of Temporary workers

Sample units not only employed permanent workers but also temporary workers. Wage payments relating to temporary workers of the sample units are presented in table 3.

Table 3 Distribution of salary of temporary workers based on selected variables

		Mean	SD	N	F	p
Sector	Large scale sector	8225556	1522074	9	127.68**	0.000
	Home scale sector	1749454.8	502159.2	28		
	Small scale sector	2821184.4	777994.8	23		
	Cottage sector	2318265.6	997194	33		

Source: Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Temporary labour cost is high in large scale sector (8225556) followed by small scale sector, cottage sector, and finally home scale sector (1749454.8). The F test has significant variation at 0.01 level (F=127.68).

To examine whether differences exist between the variables on a pair basis, Scheffe multiple comparisons are presented below.

Table 4 Scheffe multiple comparisons of temporary workers based on selected variables

		Pair	F'	Sig.
Sector	Large scale sector (A)	A & B	120.24**	0.00
	Home scale sector (B)	A & C	79.53**	0.00
	Small scale sector (C)	A & D	103.87**	0.00
	Cottage sector (D)	B & C	6.11**	0.00
		B & D	2.06	0.11
		C & D	1.44	0.24

Source: Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Scheffe multiple tests compare the temporary labour cost of large scale sector with the home scale sector show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=120.24). A similar observation can be seen, while comparing large scale with small scale (F=79.53) and large scale with cottage sector (F=103.87) at 0.01 level. A significant variation is observed in the home-scale sector with a small sector at a 0.01 level (F=6.11). While comparing the large-scale sector with other sectors, a significant difference exists in the wage payment of temporary workers, and differences also exist in home-scale with small scale. Large scale and small scale show high wages for temporary workers.

3.2 Remuneration of Technical workers

Technical workers are necessary for the units to check the quality of the products produced. Salary of technical workers based on the selected variables

Table 5 Comparison of salary of technical workers based on selected variables

		Mean	SD	N	F	p
Sector	Large scale sector	2506666.8	862090.8	9	225.82**	0.000
	Home scale sector	38571.6	57070.8	28		
	Small scale sector	146086.8	80551.2	23		
	Cottage sector	90909.6	52222.8	33		

Source: Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Labour costs of technical staff in the sample units are displayed here. As per table 4.15, technical labor costs are high in the large-scale sector (2506666.8) and low in the home scale sector (38571.6). Test show significant variation at 0.01 level (F=225.82)

The difference that exists between the selected variables can be compared on the pair base by Scheffe multiple comparisons in the following table.

Table 6 Scheffe multiple comparisons of salary of technical worker based on selected variables

		Pair	F'	Sig.
Sector	Large scale sector (A)	A & B	196.5**	0.00
	Home scale sector (B)	A & C	170.73**	0.00
	Small scale sector (C)	A & D	195.46**	0.00
	Cottage sector (D)	B & C	0.69	0.56

Source: Primary Data

** Significant at 0.01 level

Table 6 displays, Scheffe multiple comparisons of technical labor costs. Large scale with home-scale sector, large scale sector with small scale and large scale with cottage sector show significant difference 0.01

level (F=196.5). Wages of technical workers are found to be high in the large-scale sector when compared with other sectors.

4. CONCLUSION

The food processing sector in India has an essential role in linking Indian farmers to consumers in the domestic and international markets. During the last five years ending 2018-19, the Food Processing industriesector has been growing at an average growth rateof around 11.18%. As per the Annual Survey of Industries 2018-19, Food Processing was ranked 1st in total persons engaged in the sector. In Kerala mainly there are 4 sectors of FPIs, among these Large Scale sector have the labour cost found to be high. This sector has permanent workers, temporary workers, and technical workers.

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